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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable reports the comprehensive results and activities aimed to demonstrate Electron Magnetic Circular Dichroism (EMCD). It is difficult to keep the delicate OAM sorter alignment at the large energy-loss of the iron L-edge (about 700 eV). Considering also the slowdowns due to COVID-19 pandemic we opted for an equally and similar problem by looking at the difference in the σ^* and π^* transition in 2D material in the energy range of 200eV energy loss.

The kind of information and the OAM–EELS theory is fundamentally the same as real EMCD but the difficulty in the alignment is reduced. The experiment therefore succeeds in demonstrating the importance of the combination of OAM-EELS experiment also to study atomic transitions.

Considering the similarities of the two experiments this work demonstrate that EMCD is feasible and that automatic alignment procedure should soon allow to explore the energy loss range of EMCD.

For these reasons, most of this work will be of quite general interest and only a small part will regard the case of h-BN. Given the rising importance of 2D material that are now receiving even more attention than magnetic structure the result has also a large importance in its own right and fully demonstrates the potentialities of a OAM sorter in material science.

Chapter 1 will explain all the improvements we carried out in the direction of EMCD and in OAM–EELS experiments. A large space has been dedicated to the automatic control of the microscope by means of a neural network. Given the difficulties to control the many parameters, this will probably be the best way to carry out the most difficult future experiments.

Chapter 2 will explain all problems of localization and decoherence. Once again this theoretical framework is valid for all OAM–EELS experiments and is of general interest to understand our data and to design future experiments.

Chapter 3 is dedicated to effective manuscript draft with experiments and data analysis. As for the setup also the deconvolution method used in this section can be easily transported to the case of EMCD.

1 SETUP

So far the OAM sorter was always implemented in a TITAN-HOLO [1].

The TITAN HOLO has demonstrated its many advantages over any other microscope for the flexibility given by the large number of lenses in the imaging system. Beyond the image corrector it features an XL lens before the diffraction lens and an additional SAD aperture.

In the main part of the work, for this deliverable and for the whole WP4, the XL has been used as an additional projection lens in order to increase the magnification of the OAM spectrum and to have a sufficient number of pixels separating two OAM peaks.

The details of the configuration are described in D4.3.

1.1 New MEMS and holder

We will show here mainly data obtained with the TITAN HOLO but, beyond this specific case, we considered also microscopes with different optical setup and the possibility to fit the sorter into them. This has two specific reasons: 1) to be able to test the OAM sorter in Thermofisher so that more up-to-date and maintained energy filters can be tested for the operations 2) for a more general study of the feasibility of the sorter on a generic machine.

The main difficulty for introducing the sorter in a generic TEM is the space available for the first sorting element in the objective aperture. The Titan-HOLO has a cryo-type pole piece and the separation between the two pole pieces is 11 mm. That is more than enough to host aperture holders, cryo-blades and many attachments like even a cathodoluminescence apparatus. For this reason the same holder used for the SAD aperture can be used in the Objective aperture without any problem.

However, when it comes to high-resolution pole pieces, the available space is much smaller and specific solutions need to be studied.

In particular, we created two specific aperture holders that allow for introducing biasing MEMS in the objective aperture of a generic microscope (see Figure 1).

Figure 1.: Aperture holder for high-resolution objective lenses.

This device should allow the use inside the TEM but we did not have the time to test it before the end of the project because of the travel restriction caused by the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic.

At the same time different solutions are being studied within Thermofisher to provide the same kind of thin objects.

1.2 Automatic alignment and neural network

1.2 Automatic alignment and neural network

In order to optimize the resolution of the Sorter, the critical point is the alignment of the beam in the with respect to the second sorter element, as illustrated in Figure 2. The phase profile imparted to the beam by the first element of the sorter (labelled as S1) is responsible for the evolution of the beam shape during the propagation. This transformation is completed on the plane of the second element of the sorter (labelled as S2). We now want to preserve this shape of the beam as it is the correct log-polar transformation we need to exploit in order to measure the OAM. Therefore the beam should be carefully located on top of the S2 in order to perfectly compensate for the residual phase of the S1.

It follows that, if the phase compensation is not perfect, unwanted transformation might happen after this plane that will cause a reduction of the overall performance of the device in terms of OAM resolution.

Figure 2: schematic representation of the perfect alignment condition of the two sorter elements. The beam is diffracted by the first sorter element (S1) and this causes the characteristic log-polar transformation. The transformation is completed on the plane where the second element (S2) is located. The beam is here aligned with S2 in order to completely remove any residual phase of the S1. This prevents any further development of the beam shape after this plane. False colour images: the saturation represents the modulus and the hue represents the phase of the complex electron wave-function.

There are many factors that can potentially hamper the phase matching on the S2 plane. Some of them are related to the construction (e.g., the shape of the needles and their position) and can only be minimized by a careful realization of the devices. Other factors instead are related to the way the whole system (microscope and Sorter together) is aligned and their adjustment only depends on the skill of the operator. These effects include: the position of the beam (shift), the rotation angle between the beam and the S2 element (β), the focus of the lens focusing the beam on the S2 plane (df) and a scale factor defining the magnification of the beam. The latter we call size mismatch (SM) and it is directly related to the bias applied to the S1.

Each one of these parameters affect the resolution of the final OAM spectrum in a different, characteristic way as illustrated in Figure 3. The three columns show electron optical simulations

of the primary misalignments between the diffraction of S1 (left column) and S2 (centre column) and their effect on an OAM spectrum (right column). The simulations are performed for a 300 keV electron beam defined by a 2 mrad hard aperture traveling in vacuum. The sorter parameters are $s=3 \mu\text{rad}$ and $L=40 \mu\text{m}$. The algorithm that was used for the calculations is described below. The first row corresponds to the ideal situation, in which the phase of the beam is matched perfectly and compensated by the phase of element S2 (central column). The OAM spectrum then only features a narrow spot at $\ell=0$ (right column). In the second row (Figure 3b), the defocus of the objective lens (df/f) is considered. The conformal mapping is then not completed in the plane in which element S2 is located. As a result, a residual curvature is present in the beam and the phase pattern is distorted. The main effect of this aberration is a broadening of the beam in the radial direction (P_r), which depends on the sign of the defocus. The OAM resolution is preserved instead, meaning that a moderate amount of defocus can be tolerated if only the OAM component is of interest.

Figure 3: Primary misalignment conditions between the diffraction of S1 (left column) and S2 (centre column) and their effects on an OAM spectrum (right column). a) Perfect condition, with the beam and S2 aligned. b) Effect of objective lens defocus (df/f). c) Effect of size mismatch (SM). d) Effect of rigid shift (sh_x and sh_y). e) Effect of rotation (β). Scale bar in real space images: $10 \mu\text{m}$. The OAM spectrum spans a range of $40\hbar$. The real space misalignment (left column) is magnified for better visualization. The real parameters that were used for the simulation are shown as labels.

A more prominent source of resolution loss is the size mismatch (SM) between the beam and element S2 (c). This aberration appears when the electron beam scale in the S2 plane is larger (smaller) than the scale dictated by the periodicity of element S2. Since the periodicity of S2 is bound to the physical distance between the electrodes and cannot be modified, correction for this aberration entails changing the beam size. The size of the electron beam in the S2 plane, in turn, depends on the product of the focal distance between the two planes (another physical parameter that cannot be changed) and the excitation of element S1. An optimal potential then needs to be applied to the main electrode of element S1. A deviation from this value introduces an SM aberration to the OAM spectrum. The main effect of the SM aberration is the introduction of background fringes and a loss of OAM resolution. A difference of a few % is sufficient to produce the effect reported in the right column.

The third effect is associated with a rigid shift of the electron beam in one or both directions (shx and shy) with respect to element S2. The primary effect of this misalignment is an asymmetrical background fringe pattern. A misalignment of a few nm, which is small compared to the periodicity of element S2 (typically 20 μm), is sufficient to reduce the OAM resolution. Fortunately, TEMs offer high-precision control over the beam position and this aberration can be fixed easily, even manually.

The last row reports the effect of relative rotation (i.e., orientation mismatch β) of the electron beam with respect to element S2.

A manual alignment of all these parameters simultaneously is quite a challenging and time consuming task. Often it is based on a brute force approach: parameters are changed randomly to find the improvement direction. Therefore we seek a tool for fast and reliable alignment.

Deep learning approaches using convolutional neural networks (CNNs) [2, 3] have recently proven to be a powerful tool for image classification and analysis of microscopy data.[4,5,6] Several studies have shown that deep learning-based estimation of optical aberrations can produce accurate results to be used in automatic alignment of adaptive optics apparatus, [7,8] thanks to the high computational efficiency and speed of CNN. They are able to learn from a large set of training images to extrapolate a detail or the value of a parameter tagged to each image.[9,10] It is able to treat complex parametric spaces, if enough high-quality training data are available for the learning algorithm. It is also often more robust to noise than an analytical model. Following these ideas, we trained a CNN to recognize the main misalignments from a single OAM spectrum and to provide a list of corrective parameters. The CNN was then linked to the microscope so that such corrections can be directly implemented, realizing the automatic alignment of the device.

The CNN that we connected to the microscope and voltage generator is composed by a total of 13 layers (schematically shown in Figure 4): an input layer (a 128x128 pixel image), 5 convolution layer filters (each one followed by an average-pooling layer filter) and two fully connected layers lead to the output, corresponding to a total of 2,480,326 trainable parameters. The chosen activation function was the rectified linear unit (ReLU), the learning algorithm used was Adam, the learning rate was 0.001, while the loss function was the root mean square difference between the predicted misalignment coefficients and the true coefficients.

The neural network was implemented using the Keras library [11] and the TensorFlow backend.[12]

Figure 4: Convolution Neural Network layout.

In order to train a neural network of this size, a database of training examples containing several thousands of images is required. As a general rule of deep learning, the performances of any neural network are as good as the data on which it is trained upon.

In order to produce a training dataset, a numerical method was implemented to simulate the OAM spectroscopy experiment based on a full wave calculation and free space propagation, to describe the effects of different aberrations and misalignments on the final resolution. The beam was free-space propagated between the elements using the Fresnel-Kirchhoff integral

$$U_z(u, v) = \frac{e^{ikz}}{i\lambda z} \iint U_0(x, y) e^{-ik\frac{xu+yv}{z}} dx dy$$

whereas the lenses were defined by quadratic phase elements of the form

$$T = \exp\left(\frac{i(x^2 + y^2)}{2f\lambda}\right)$$

Calculations were performed numerically on an 8k x 8k mesh using a Fourier transform algorithm for convolutions. Versions of the code were written in Matlab (for testing purposes) and C (for fast parallel computing). The phase shift associated with S1 can be described mathematically by the expression:

$$\varphi_{S1}(x, y) = \frac{kS}{f} \left(y \frac{y}{x} - x \log \log \left(\frac{\sqrt{x^2 + y^2}}{L} \right) + x \right)$$

where k is the electron wavevector, f is the focal distance between the two sorter elements and s and L are scaling parameters [13]. The phase shift introduced by element S2 can be written in the form

$$\varphi_{S2}(u, v) = -\frac{k s L}{f} e^{-\frac{u}{s}} \cos \cos \left(\frac{v}{s} \right)$$

where u and v are coordinates in the diffraction plane. This numerical formalism allows us to easily model the different aberration by acting of the x and y coordinates (for shifts and rotation), on the lens focal f and the excitation parameter of the sorter s .

Figure 5: Demonstration of the predictive ability of the CNN for a comparison between simulated reference images (upper row) and simulations performed using the parameters predicted by the CNN (lower row).

A database of 20,000 simulated images (+ 2000 images for validation purposes) was produced. A few entries from the database are reported in Fig 5, upper row. The CNN was trained on the simulation database for 20 cycles through the full training dataset.

In order to validate the fitting accuracy of the CNN, the predicted misalignment coefficients were fed back into the simulation algorithm. The resulting images (Fig 5, lower row) are in good agreement with the real images.

A similar test has been then repeated on experimental images. The results are reported in figure 6. Also in this case we can appreciate a nice qualitative match between the experimental images (top row) and the one produced following the parameters inferred by the neural network (lower row).

Figure 6: Demonstration of the predictive ability of the CNN for a comparison between experimental images (upper row) and simulations performed using the parameters predicted by the CNN (lower row).

For a more quantitative evaluation of the neural network fitting ability we selected a few parameters and we varied them in a symmetric range around the central point provided by our best manual alignment. An image was acquired for every configuration and fitted using the CNN. In figure 7 the cases of SM aberration and defocus are reported. We selected these two aberrations in particular because they are the ones that we can control with the highest accuracy. In both cases the expected linear trend between the estimated values and the real one applied to the system suggests successful fitting of the sorter misalignments.

Figure 7: Comparison between experimental sorter parameters and CNN predictions shown as a function of a) S1 main potential and b) defocus (df/f).

At this point it is worth mentioning that the fitting of an experimental image using the CNN only takes a few tens of millisecond on a normal pc. The computational time is therefore negligible compared to the acquisition time. Combining the predictive ability of the CNN and its speed we

can aim to a the real-time control of the system during experiments, by integrating the CNN with the microscope control system.

For this reason we implemented the following control loop (see Figure 8). Image data from the microscope is fed into the CNN, and the output of the CNN is converted to control commands that are fed to the microscope and connected devices via suitable application programming interfaces (APIs). As an overview, the control loop can be described by the following steps:

1. An image is acquired from the camera
2. The image is pre-processed
3. The pre-processed image is fed into the neural network
4. The network determines the parameters that it expects to perfectly align the sorter
5. The corrections are applied as changes to microscope parameters and voltage source.

Figure 8: control loop for real time alignment of the Sorter.

Image data acquisition: For data acquisition, a K2 camera is operated in In-Situ mode (IS mode). A prototype of a K2-IS adapter for the LiberTEM-live framework is used [14]. It allows for continuous data capture and analysis at the full data rate of the K2-IS camera (400 fps at 2048x1860). For this work, 400 images were summed up to form a 1 second exposure image for each control step.

Image pre-processing: After acquisition, the images are pre-processed so that they match the images in the training dataset in size and orientation. A precise calibration is crucial for the CNN to provide quantitative results. To this aim, calibration spectra have been obtained using beams with a known OAM decomposition. Once the pixel size of the experimental images is measured, they can be scaled, cropped, and then normalized in the interval [0,1] to match with the simulations in the training dataset.

Inference: The network predicts the corrections that it expects to lead to perfect alignment of the sorter. [15] These settings are applied relative to the current state of the system with a damping factor and rate limit to tolerate calibration errors and manage interdependence between the

parameters. Dampening prevents overshooting the target, thus limiting in most of the cases the jumps around the convergence point. Such jumps are expected since the network was trained with a limited resolution. For User Beam Shift (X/Y) and for the intensity a dampening factor of 0.4 was used. For controlling the S1 value of the sorter, we adopted a smaller dampening factor of 0.2. Such value is the most sensitive parameter.

Instruments control: Multiple devices are controlled for the experiment. In order to power the two sorter devices a 16-channel voltage source was used (a Stahl-Electronics' DC precision voltage source BS-series). While the TEM parameters (User Beam Shift (X/Y), C3 intensity and possibly other parameters) are controlled via the COM scripting interface of the microscope. All devices, with the exception of the K2 camera, were controlled using a Tango setup [16]. Tango allows network-transparent control of different devices and encapsulates the actual control details into the tango device server. After the device server is written and set up, it can be used by installing a Tango client library, from any of the supported languages. On the client side, there are no further hardware-specific dependencies.

Figure 9: Experimental image series showing how the OAM spectrum evolves in time as the NN provides the corrective values. On the top left corner is reported the frame number, and as an overlay on the bottom left corner are the value of the detrimental parameters estimated by the NN that were fed to the microscope to obtain the successive frame. As an overlay in the last shown

frame is reported the peak line scan: the width of the Gaussian profile equal to two times the standard deviation is 1.68 \AA .

Finally in Figure 9 we report a series of images proving the efficiency of our automatic alignment setup. We started on purpose from the misaligned condition (frame 0) and asked the NN to correct the OAM spectrum. Here we only controlled three parameters: the size mismatch (i.e., the voltage applied to the main needle of the Unwrapper) and the User Beam Shift (X/Y). It only takes 10 frames to complete the alignment.

1.3 Toward the auto-alignment in energy loss condition

Figure 10: Sequence of energy filtered OAM spectra at 290 eV loss for successive correction of the sorter alignment.

One of the most important applications of the automatic alignment would be for EELS images. The images above (fig 10) have been obtained by keeping the probe voltage at 300KeV and looking and energy loss of 290 eV. We have therefore the sorter in out-of-tune conditions. The images are obtained in the carbon loss region with a typical exposure time of 10 s and with a spot size 7 (having larger current and lower C1 condenser excitation than standard spot 9) so much more incoherent than in standard (spot 9) sorter operations. This has been done in order to increase the signal noise ratio.

We show that the alignment improved from left to right after lengthy operation that would have been strongly facilitated by an automatic procedure allowing for a few long exposure acquisition.

Fitting this in many core loss conditions could also be used as a training for the neural network to extrapolate down to 700eV energy loss condition for EMCD experiment.

The use of a less coherent probe is also something we need to analyze in further detail in view of the coherence consideration in the chapter 2.

2 Delocalization and coherence

We have already tackled in D4.2 the theory of EMCD in material but somehow this theory was a complex computing algorithm for crystalline materials that hides the mechanism of localization

and does not allow to understand the conditions at which OAM can be measured in inelastically scattered waves.

Here we developed in greater detail the case of a simple scatterer removing all dynamical effects. This simplification permits to better understand the OAM-EELS spectra when the probe is not concentrated on a single column.

This description also permits to simulate and account for the broadening effects that are introduced in the OAM spectrum. This is the first step to remove these effects and to produce a clean OAM spectrum. This is also a necessary step to understand the use of the OAM –sorter with and without atomic resolution, the role of post selection and the ideal convergence/ detection conditions.

2.1 MDFF and localization

In this section we start from the Mixed dynamic form factor description of inelastic scattering to demonstrate that the inelastic scattering acts by localizing the wave to a function centered on atoms. The EELS cross section is described in terms of Mixed dynamic form factor (MDFF) here indicated by S as [17]

$$\frac{\partial^2 \sigma}{\partial E \partial \Omega} \propto \frac{S(Q, Q', \omega)}{Q^2 Q'^2} \quad (1)$$

Where $Q = (\underline{k}_f - \underline{k}_i, q_{\Delta E})$ and $Q' = (\underline{k}_f' - \underline{k}_i', q_{\Delta E}')$ are 3D-vectors and account for kinematical effects of exchange of momentum $\underline{k}_f, \underline{k}_i$ and energy through $q_{\Delta E} = \Delta E / (\hbar v)$ where ΔE is the energy loss, v is the electron velocity \hbar is the reduced Planck constant, and v is the electron velocity. $q_{\Delta E}$ is also related to the characteristic scattering angle by the relation $q_E = 2\pi\theta_E/\lambda$, where λ is the electron. The $1/Q^2$ produces a Lorentzian-like envelope on the dependence on exchanged momentum $\underline{q} = \underline{k}_f - \underline{k}_i$ that concentrates the scattering angle within characteristic scattering angle θ_E .

All the atomic details are included in S , the mixed dynamic form factor. A crude dipole approximation in highly symmetric systems and for a single atom in the origin is given by [17]:

$$S(Q, Q', \omega) \approx A(\omega) \underline{Q} \cdot \underline{Q}' + B(\omega) \quad (2)$$

where $A(\omega)$ and $B(\omega)$ are two energy dependent coefficients. After the scattering, the beam-atomic state is non-separable [18]. We assume here a single scattering and the electron subsystem can be therefore described by a reduced density matrix ρ [19]

$$\rho(k_f, k_f) = \frac{S(Q, Q', \omega)}{Q^2 Q'^2} * \rho_0(k_i, k_i) \quad (3)$$

As a function of the initial pure state probe (here described by the $\rho_0(k_i, k_i) = |\psi_{ep}\rangle \langle \psi_{ep}|$) that is an equivalent way of writing the pure state of the probe $|\psi_{ep}\rangle$.

When detecting the electrons in the OAM basis this expression is very difficult to use as it implies a re-projection on the OAM basis. A common approach in optics, carried on also by Schattschneider [20], is not to describe the full density matrix evolution but, instead, to diagonalize the density matrix in the form $\rho = \sum_{\alpha} |\psi_{e\alpha}\rangle\langle\psi_{e\alpha}|$ [20]. Each eigenstate $|\psi_{e\alpha}\rangle$ is a pure state and its propagation for example, in our OAM sorter, can be followed numerically. In the case of core atomic transition each α label corresponds to a single atom.

We will show in the next session that the $|\psi_{e\alpha}\rangle$ can be written as the product of the probe wavefunction and a localization function f , namely

$$|\psi_{e\alpha}\rangle = f(\underline{r} - \underline{r}_{\alpha})|\psi_p\rangle$$

2.2 Density matrix diagonalization

A series of simplifications occur because we are in the single scattering case with no additional elastic scattering. The density matrix in diagonal representation would be

$$\rho = \sum_{\alpha} |\psi_{\alpha}\rangle\langle\psi_{\alpha}|. \quad (4)$$

Having a diagonal representation is relevant in the case of OAM decomposition because the representation on a series of pure states allows for an easier change of basis.

We demonstrate here (consistently with literature) that in separate atom scattering conditions and with no further elastic / inelastic scattering the density matrix has eigenvectors (for an atom in the origin)

$$|\psi_{e\alpha}\rangle = f(\underline{r}) \cdot |\psi_{ep}\rangle. \quad (5)$$

To demonstrate this let's we rewrite it in the $k_{i,f}$ basis. k_i are those of the probe so that symbolically we can write

$$|\psi_{ep}\rangle = \sum_{k_i \in \text{Aperture}} |\underline{k}_i\rangle. \quad (6)$$

The detection is extended between $k_i \in [0, \frac{\beta_{in}}{\lambda}]$ the detection is $k_f \in [0, \frac{\beta_{out}}{\lambda}]$

The density matrix in this new basis is

$$\rho = \sum_{\underline{k}_f, \underline{k}_f', \alpha} |\underline{k}_f\rangle\langle\underline{k}_f| \psi_{e\alpha}\rangle\langle\psi_{e\alpha}| \underline{k}_f'\rangle\langle\underline{k}_f'| \quad (7)$$

The central part of the formula $\langle\underline{k}_f|\psi_{e\alpha}\rangle$ is written as the Fourier transform of $|\psi_{e\alpha}\rangle$

The product in direct space of eq 5 becomes a convolution in Fourier space for the aperture function

$A = \int \psi_{ep} \exp(ikr) dr$ and the scattering function $G = \int \psi_{e\alpha} \exp(ikr) dr$ that is just a Lorentzian or Gaussian function with factor $q_{\Delta E}$.

In the k representation ψ becomes $A(k_i) \otimes G(k_f) = \int A(k_i) \tilde{G}(k_f - k_i) dk_i = \int \tilde{P}(k_i) \tilde{G}(q) dk_i$. The convolution and the appearance of the factor $\underline{q} = \underline{k}_f - \underline{k}_i$ lead us to the familiar expression, where

$\langle k_i k_f | \psi_{e\alpha} \rangle \langle \psi_{e\alpha} | k_i k_f \rangle$ is therefore the factor $\frac{s(Q, Q', \omega)}{Q^2 Q'^2}$.

It is possible also to separate the MDFF for each atom outside the center as $MDFF = \sum_{\alpha} \frac{s(Q, Q', \omega)}{Q^2 Q'^2} \exp [i (\underline{Q} - \underline{Q}') \underline{r}_{\alpha}]$. (8)

Since the MDFF depends only on the factor \underline{q} , it is written as a convolution in momentum space, i.e. it can be considered as a multiplicative effect in real space. If the initial wavefunction is multiplied by a new narrower function that is given by $f(\underline{r})$ the effect of scattering will be to “collapse” the wave on such a function. An effective scattered wave is obtained by the product

$$|\psi_{e\alpha}\rangle = f(\underline{r}) \cdot |\psi_{ep}\rangle. \quad (9)$$

Conversely the projection on the final detection state of the overall density matrix is given by a product in reciprocal space and a convolution in real space.

The final OAM state of the detection would then be described by the further reduced density matrix

$$\rho(l, l') = \sum_{k_f, k'_f \in Det} \langle k_f l | \rho | k'_f l' \rangle, \quad (10)$$

whose diagonal elements are our spectrum.

2.3 MDFF approximations

Here we describe the MDFF approximation that simplify our calculations.

The MDFF in the simplest form of dipole approximation is given by

$$MDFF = \frac{a \underline{Q} \cdot \underline{Q}' + b}{Q^2 Q'^2} \quad (11)$$

However, we can rewrite it as

$$MDFF = \frac{a \underline{q} \cdot \underline{q}' + c}{(q^2 + q_E^2)(q'^2 + q'_E{}^2)}$$

$$MDFF = \frac{a q q' \cos(\Delta\phi) + c}{(q^2 + q_E^2)(q'^2 + q'_E{}^2)}$$

$$= \frac{a q q' \exp(i\phi) \exp(-i\phi')}{(q^2 + q_E^2)(q'^2 + q'_E{}^2)} + \frac{a q q' \exp(-i\phi) \exp(i\phi')}{(q^2 + q_E^2)(q'^2 + q'_E{}^2)} + \frac{c}{(q^2 + q_E^2)(q'^2 + q'_E{}^2)} \quad (12)$$

The Fourier transform would give the rMDF. For the calculation it is convenient to Fourier transform each term separately. In fact, in many cases we will measure only OAM so the relative coherence of these terms is less important but can be considered anyway. We will then Fourier transform the twofactorized functions depending on the q , q' variables separately.

The problem therefore is transferred into finding the (inverse) Fourier transform of g

$$g(\underline{q}) = \frac{a q^n \exp(in\phi)}{(q^2 + q_E^2)} \quad (13)$$

The (inverse) Fourier transform with respect to separate terms is based on the 0th and 1st order Hankel transform H through the formula

$$H_0 \left\{ \frac{c}{(q^2 + q_E^2)} \right\} = c K_0(q_E r), \quad (14a)$$

$$H_1 \left\{ \frac{a q}{(q^2 + q_E^2)} \right\} = a q_E K_1(q_E r). \quad (14b)$$

Both the Modified Bessel functions of second kind can be approximated for large r by $K(x) \propto \frac{1}{\sqrt{x}} \exp(-x)$. Therefore the 3 terms would give rise to a real space distribution $f(\underline{r}) \approx \frac{\exp(\pm i l \phi_\alpha) \exp(-|\underline{r} - \underline{r}_\alpha|/d)}{\sqrt{|\underline{r} - \underline{r}_\alpha|}}$

Notice that both the functions $K_n(q_E r)$ have a divergence at $r=0$ that is due to the limits of the approximations of S especially in neglecting the radial degrees of freedom. A common but still approximated way to account for these limits is to impose a cutoff at $|\Delta \underline{r}_c| = \frac{\lambda}{2\pi\sqrt{2}\theta_E}$.

Another way to approach the same problem is to consider $\frac{1}{q^2 + q_E^2} \approx \exp\left[-\frac{q^2}{q_E^2}\right]$ so that the function g becomes

$$g(\underline{q}) \approx a q^n \exp(in\phi) \exp\left[-\frac{q^2}{q_E^2}\right] \quad (15)$$

This is a Laguerre Gauss beam that transforms into a Laguerre Gauss beam with the same n .

$$f(\underline{r}) \approx N |\underline{r} - \underline{r}_\alpha|^{|l|} \exp(\pm i l \phi_\alpha) \exp(-|\underline{r} - \underline{r}_\alpha|^2/d^2) \quad (16)$$

where $d=1/q_E$ is the delocalization parameter.

It should be noticed that this approximation has a strong limitation in the fact that it describes the scattering with a single parameter q_E^2 while $\Delta \underline{r}_c$ is not considered. However it must be stressed

that even the cutoff approach would in any case not reproduce the final results. In the rest of this material we will assume that

$$MDFF = g(\underline{q})g(\underline{q}') = FT(f(\underline{r}))FT(f(\underline{r}')) \quad (17)$$

2.4 OAM indetermination at general conditions

In this section we calculate how much OAM uncertainty is produced by the inelastic scattering.

This calculation assumes in particular that the position of the scattering atoms that localizes the wavefunction is not centered on the optical axis.

Since the commutator $[L_z, x] = i\hbar y$ we can write the uncertainty principle for the OAM as $\sigma_L \geq \hbar \frac{\langle y \rangle}{\sigma}$

The atom position and therefore the center of the inelastically scattered wave is shifted by $\langle y \rangle$. For a broad probe, larger than the atomic distances more atom can contribute so this assumes the form of blurring of the atomic position. If the probe size is R we can estimate in a pessimistic way $\langle y \rangle \approx R$. We investigate here how much this blurring affects the final OAM spectrum.

The parameters are therefore the spatial extent of the probe. The delocalization in absence of forms of post-selection of the scattering angle (or super localization for very narrow probe) is simply $\sigma = d$.

So it is natural to expect that as an optimal experiment is for $R = d$ since further reducing the probe would also reduce the value of σ .

In facts when the probe size $R < d$ and the probe sits exactly on the atom, the post scattering wavefunction $|\psi_{e\alpha}\rangle$ is practically truncated roughly to the probe size.

Moreover it is worth reminding that if the probe is very small and located exactly on the atom the uncertainty of the OAM is zero.

$$\sigma_L \geq \hbar \frac{0}{R} = 0. \quad (18)$$

Conversely if the probe is randomly located within the probe and $R = d$

$$\sigma_L \geq \hbar \frac{R}{R} = 1\hbar. \quad (19)$$

Finally we can calculate what would happen if the collection angle β_{out} is reduced. This is equivalent to broaden the value of σ to $\sigma = \frac{\lambda}{2\pi\beta_{out}}$ so that the full indetermination can be written for a probe not centered on atoms as

$$\sigma_L \geq \hbar \frac{\beta_{out}}{\beta_{in}}, \quad (20)$$

Where we assumed that the probe size is mainly diffraction limited.

We can also include all cases in a compact formula

$$\sigma_L \geq \hbar \frac{1}{\beta_{in} \sqrt{1/\beta_{eff}^2 + 1/\beta_{out}^2}}, \quad (21)$$

$$\text{where } \beta_{eff} = \sqrt{\theta_E^2 + \beta_{in}^2}.$$

The quadrature $\sqrt{1/\beta_{eff}^2 + 1/\beta_{out}^2}$ here derives from the fact that the final state effect is the convolution of the detector effect and the truncated $|\psi_{e\alpha}\rangle$ extension.

Notice that the same uncertainty principle would occur on scattering experiments using a vortex probe and integrating over a small detection angle.

Notice also that if post selection is appropriately used it is also possible to use larger current and decrease the coherence since the actual scattering function departing from each atom is little affected by the coherence of the impinging wave that only defines how many atoms are contributing to the scattering.

It would not be impossible to find a condition for which the inelastically scattered electrons are more coherent than the impinging beam.

3 Manuscript: experimental data on h-BN

The rotational invariance is one of the fundamental symmetries of nature both in vacuum and in presence of central potentials as in the case of atoms. Therefore, the best paradigm for atomic transition measurement would be to measure the variation of the orbital angular momentum (OAM) that is the generator of rotational symmetries. Thanks to innovative electron optics device called ‘‘OAM sorter’’ it is now possible for the first time to combine the energy loss spectroscopy (EELS) at nm scale with OAM measurement in a single extended spectral measurement. Due to its natural coupling to the atomic symmetries this idea presents strong advantages with respect to linear momentum resolved EELS. Here we show experimentally the possibility to separate the π^* and σ^* anti-bonding transitions in hexagonal Boron Nitride (h-BN) with a single acquisition without the need to tilt the sample. The new technique and instrument will permit us to separate in a natural way different multipolar transitions and efficiently measure magnetic chiral dichroism.

The energy loss spectroscopy within an electron microscope is one of the most powerful measurement tools in material science because it combines the spectroscopy with the possibility to probe atomic properties on the very local scale. In particular accurate EELS analysis allow to investigate the composition, the chemical valence and the level occupation.

The electromagnetic nature of the electron-matter interaction permits us to describe the energy loss process as an optical absorption with the advantage that a single probe can analyze the range from few meV [21] to core levels absorption at KeV scale [22,23].

In the second quantization terms the absorption of the virtual photon produced by the swift electrons of the electron beam is largely equivalent to the real photon absorption. The analogy can be further developed considering that in the selection rules of optical absorption the polarization of the real photon is substituted by the momentum variation of the swift electron. This analogy has been elegantly restated in a recent paper [24].

But it is exactly by looking at this analogy that we discover that while most of the selection rules in atomic transitions are expressed in terms of circular polarization of the photon, the same selection rules must be written in terms of the component of the angular momentum of the electrons along the main propagation direction L_z .

The eigenstates of this operator $L_z|\psi\rangle = l\hbar|\psi\rangle$ are characterized by the discrete spectrum characterized by the winding number l and are the well-known vortex beam [25-29]. The connection between vortex beams and atomic transitions has been strongly motivated, from the very beginning, the creation of such beams and more recently the realisation of an instrument that allowed the direct measurement of the OAM of inelastically scattered electrons, possibly along with the energy itself. Different solutions have been proposed for the orbital angular momentum (OAM) measurement [30-33]. The use of a pitchfork holograms for example could allow us to carry out a lossy and semi-quantitative measurement of the smallest OAM components of a beam [34]. However this technique is quite inefficient and it does not decouple completely the radial and the angular dependence of the beam. In other words the OAM decomposition of the beam cannot be evaluated quantitatively as the radial degree of freedom cannot be easily integrated.

The best solution is the OAM sorter that performs a log-polar conformal mapping to map the OAM momentum in linear moment that can be natively measured in an electron microscope [1,35,36]. The transformation is obtained, in the geometrical optic approximation, by two relatively simple phase inducing elements that impart the transformation and remove the transformation phase after diffraction. These elements can be simply added by inserting new appropriately designed electrostatic electrodes on the beam path [37,38].

Such a measurement, in spite of its complication, has now reached a high level of accuracy and partial automatization through Neural Network auto-alignment [15] so that our group could recently reach the near maximum theoretical resolution of $\otimes L = 1.1\hbar$ [39].

Analyzing simultaneously the energy loss and the OAM of inelastically scattered electrons will enable a novel series of innovative experiments in many different fields from plasmonic [40] and biomolecular systems [41], to the study of magnetic materials [42,43]. The latter technique is known as Electron Magnetic Circular Dichroism (EMCD): it is an explicit example of electron-photon analogy since it maps into the XMCD measurement that is a well-established X-ray absorption technique for magnetic measurements. The main aim of this technique is to produce a measurement of the asymmetry between the transition with angular momentum exchange $+1\hbar$ and $-1\hbar$ in the L_{2,3} edge of magnetic material [44,45]. This permits to evaluate the spin population in a material. It is a sought for technique in the road-map of electron microscopy future development [46].

In this paper we aim to demonstrate the possibility of a joint OAM and EELS measurement for the first time.

For this experiment an OAM sorter has been inserted in the post-specimen part of the microscope and the OAM spectrum has been energy filtered so that the energy loss and the OAM can be read on the two axes of the image. An experimental example is here shown in fig 1 with the low-loss spectrum of amorphous carbon with the volume plasmon loss clearly visible and centered around the OAM value $l = 0$. We also added a structured illumination (a petal beam with $l = \pm 4$) to demonstrate that the OAM can be measured also on the inelastically scattered electrons.

As a test sample we focused on the Boron K-edge in 2D hexagonal Boron Nitride (h-BN), to give a first experimental demonstration of the new technique and its unique potentialities. The case study of a 2D-material is a very relevant one, due to its possible applications and structural and electrical unique features [47].

At the origin of these properties there is the peculiar form of the bond that is based on the sp^2 hybridization of the atomic orbitals that form the σ and π bonding orbitals and the σ^* and π^* antibonding states.

The hybridized orbitals have a complex shape but the original symmetry of atomic level is maintained so that, when the quantization axis is chosen orthogonal to the 2D plane, σ^* and π^* are characterized by a dominant value of magnetic quantum number $m = \pm 1$ and $m = 0$ respectively. Therefore for EELS experiments with the beam aligned and centered on the quantization axis, the transitions from the occupied $1s$ state to those antibonding states are well-characterized in terms of final electron state being characterized by winding numbers $l = \pm 1$ and $l = 0$, respectively.

The two transitions have slightly different energy onsets (by roughly 8 eV in the Boron K-edge) so in common EELS experiments, where only energy-loss is observed, the details of the post-edge features are not directly separable. Linear-momentum-dispersed experiments could add partial information but require a very large momentum precision and this means, in many cases, a near plane wave illumination and/or a small pupil aperture. An alternative is approaching the layer from side view with a cross-section or by tilting the sample, to distinguish the out-of-plane different contributions [48,49]. Conversely, the additional OAM dispersion available in the experiment presented here allows for a 2D plot where the two edges are separated as well as for the determination of the energy distribution of the residual contribution from the $m = 0$ part of the σ^* state.

Figure 11 Scheme of the experiment, on the left the microscope configuration. Top center is the scheme of the BN atoms. Right is the orbital configuration and the corresponding energy scheme-

3.1 Deconvolution method

The theory in chapter 2 explains that the scattering from different atoms gives rise to a set of incoherent wavefunctions departing around each atoms. We explain here how, in spite of this complex process we can retrieve the average angular momentum exchange of the transitions.

Figure 12 Scheme of the incoherent OAM spectrum formation for a scattering from more incoherent atoms.

Figure 12 explains how the localization on different atoms affects the OAM spectrum if more atoms can scatter within the probe. The probe localizes on each atom and give rise to a different OAM spectrum that depends on how much the atom is distant from the optical axis.

This gives rise to a complex OAM distribution but univocally determined for any scattering rule of the atom. So an inversion algorithm can be devised to retrieve which was the probability of the original winding numbers of the ensemble of atoms.

The data we have taken are still affected by a relatively strong OAM uncertainty. This is due to the lack of a proper sorter entrance aperture. The smart selection of bias for the element S2 allows us to limit a collection angle to roughly 3 mrad which is still not enough to have resolution of $1\hbar$. As a solution we can use a parameter based deconvolution.

The raw data looks like the image below. The image features the B K-edge with the two sub-edges. The vertical coordinate is the OAM. We also plotted the same graph but we normalized so as to have slices corresponding to each energy normalized to the maximum intensity in OAM.

Figure 13 Raw data of the OAM-EELS spectrum. Same data but normalizing each for each energy to its maximum

These raw data indicate that even if the central pixel that corresponds to an apparent OAM $L=0$ is always dominating, the first edge (π^* edge) is characterized by a narrower spectrum in the OAM direction. This is visible as a “neck” in the spectrum in correspondence of the first edge. The consideration in figure 12 explain while the peak at the center is dominating. The actual OAM at the atomic level can be extracted by a deconvolution process. In particular apparently the second edge after deconvolution to be dominated by the ± 1 contribution. To describe this we need numerical simulations.

3.2 Simulation and fitting

The simulations are based on all assumptions so far: each atom scatters independently producing a LG beam centered in the atomic position. Considering the fact that we did not measure the probe position in the lattice and that drift is often larger than one lattice parameters, the atoms are randomly distributed along the probe and the average OAM spectrum is calculated. We considered atoms with intrinsic values of ℓ in the interval $[-2, 2]$, the scattering centers are equally distributed in a radius of 0.5 nm and that the delocalization area is 0.3 nm. The resulting OAM distributions for each ℓ component

are shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14. Distributions of the five components with $\ell \in [-2, 2]$ after propagation through the OAM Sorter as a consequence of the finite size of the probe.

Of course we cannot resolve the single OAM but deterministically we can calculate the mixing combination of the five peaks. Note that because of the cutoff the $\ell=1$ is much less intense than $\ell=0$ so the weight has to take this into account.

We fitted the five peaks with a fixed OAM position and fixed model. Considering the curves above even a small contribution of the $\ell=0$ dominates.

This means that even a small contribution with $L=0$ appears huge in the spectra and the differences are only on the sides.

Mathematically we can say that if the intrinsic OAM distribution is $\sigma = \sum_l c_l(E) |l\rangle$. The measured quantity is

$$I(l, E) = i c_l(E) w_i(l), \quad (17)$$

where w_i is the weight due to the sorting system. The fitting automatically leaves the coefficient c_l as the only free parameters. In our case, we have only five free parameters that are the weight for each curve and no other free parameter.

3.3 Result

The elaboration produces the OAM-EELS map shown in fig. 15 (top part). It can be directly compared with the theoretical calculation in the bottom part of fig. 15.

To interpret this graph, we must consider that due the unoccupied states are of three types namely: s , p_z and $p_{x,y}$. While the transition to s and p_z are not characterized by no change in the electron OAM, the transition to $p_{x,y}$ produces a ± 1 signature in the OAM spectrum.

The profile shows that the edge is indeed corresponding to π^* state with p_z kind of symmetry and are therefore consistently characterized by a strong isolated peak at $\otimes\ell=0$. Conversely the peak at $\otimes\ell=1$ correspondent to both s and $p_{x,y}$ kind of final state. This means that a strong component at $\otimes\ell=\pm 1$ is accompanied to a peak at $\otimes\ell=0$. The small energy difference cannot be appreciated within the necessary binning condition we used in this experiment and in any case the $\otimes\ell=0$ component at this energy is small.

In spite of this and the imperfections in the deconvolution the similarity with calculation is quite impressive.

To conclude we have shown the first OAM resolved EELS experiment on a h-BN atomic layer. We demonstrated the direct mapping of the final state's orbital angular momentum which has no comparison so far in any TEM technique. The result has been obtained with a 1nm probe size but limiting (and digitally deconvolving) the effect of position uncertainty of the atoms within the probe. This result has been possible thanks to a deconvolution and modeling based on an innovative use of the diagonalization of the density matrix of the inelastic scattering.

Beyond the separation of σ and π orbitals these results open the road to EMCD measurements and or the characterization of higher-order transitions (e.g. quadrupolar) even in the low-scattering angle regime that so far are impossible because superimposed to stronger dipolar components. The technique also will make it possible, in atomic resolution scanning experiments, to post-select dipolar transition still using with a large integration angle [50].

Figure 15. Experimental (top) and simulated (bottom) OAM spectrum as a function of the energy.

CONCLUSIONS

To conclude, we have clarified the mechanisms of formation of the OAM-EELS spectra even in the case of non-atomic scale experiments. The key of these experiments will be the post-selection i.e., the limitation of the detection angle, that will allow us to ignore the small misalignment of the atoms with respect to the optical axis. Details on the post-selection ideas have been given also in dD4.3.

Considering the detailed model, the simulation, the new holder for moving experiments in Thermofisher, the large improvement in the automatic experiments, and the prospect for a fully automatic experiment at variable energy, we are confident that EMCD is very close to success in demonstration.

Meanwhile, the measures at the boron K-edge of 2D material are a fresh, scientifically appealing result that would be sufficient alone to motivate the use of the OAM sorter.

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ANNEX 1: Referee

Referee 1

The work is very promising and I think it will really be an outstanding paper. How far is the actual EMCD?

In principle what we need is to be sure that everything is aligned at 700 eV of energy loss. The fact that we can use a larger current (smaller spot size) and still get results thanks to post selection is probably the biggest discovery in this deliverable that makes this result very close.

Most of this deliverable regards non-atomic resolution OAM-EELS. Is there hope to get atomically resolved results?

This is correct. we are extending the OAM_EELS beyond the initial idea of sole atomic resolution because it is experimentally easier.

The main problems are the alignment the stability and the signal to noise ration. It is safe to imagine that a.i. approach will solve the alignment problem. For the s/n ratio we can count on the same factors that have made atomically resolved EELS for far core loss edge a simpler work: a larger convergence and a direct detection camera can increase by more than one order of magnitude the s/n ratio and make the experiment possible.

An additional note also is for the spectrometer. The one available in the HOLO microscope is relatively old: a newest generation of spectrometer make the alignment of the OAM-EELS spectrum much easier and stable.

What is the final journal you would like to submit to in the best scenario?

The paper is meant for a journal like Nature Material or Nature physics because we think the interest of h-BN application is very large.

In passing the interest of a.i.control of the microscope is also very important and the paper we published on this topics has attracted a lot of attention.

In Deliverable D4.3 you have shown the OAM-EELS for structured illumination in the low loss region. What happens when you use the same illumination for the core loss?

We have some initial data that seem to indicate that the vortex structure is completely lost. This is not completely clear and we need further investigation.

Referee 2

I think this is a huge amount of theoretical and experimental work,

I was very interested in the a.i. implementation for microscope control. How do you plan to take care of rotation and adjust it experimentally?

We used the lenses of the corrector that is basically off but some lenses can be freely excited to take care of the rotation. In particular since the rotation depends linearly with current and the focal changes as $1/i^2$ a small excitation of the lens produces mainly a rotation and only marginally a change of the focus.

This is a medium term solution but on a long term a full column control by artificial intelligence will be necessary.

The resolution of a OAM sorter cannot be better than 1 quanta and there is still a lot of cross talk. I appreciate that deconvolution methods work very well in your case but I think it would be nice to find a way to increase resolution if possible. Is there any basic principle hampering OAM resolution beyond 1 quanta.

We have shown in the beginning of this project an idea of holographic "fan-out" sorter that could push the resolution beyond the current scheme to less than $\Delta l < 0.5$ but implementing this in the electrostatic case could be more complicated. Some ideas involve a more complicated S1 elements some other the use of an additional aperture before S1. There is not a clear solution yet but it is clear that there is not a fundamental limitation.

ANNEX 2: ABBREVIATIONS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
National Research Council (Project scientific coordinator)	Italy	CNR
Forschungszentrum Jülich, Ernst Ruska-Centre for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons	Germany	FZJ
FEI - Thermo Fisher Scientific	The Netherlands	FEI
The Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light	Germany	MPI
University of Glasgow, Department of Physics and Astronomy	United Kingdom	UG
QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd. - UK	United Kingdom	QED
University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Department of Physics, Informatics, and Mathematics - IT	Italy	UMR

Maastricht University, Maastricht MultiModal Molecular Imaging Inst	The Netherlands	MU
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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL